

**THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN THE THEORY OF CONCEPTUAL
METAPHOR AND CONCEPTUAL INTEGRATION**

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Annotation: The article deals with the theories that have become classics of cognitive linguistics - the theory of conceptual metaphor (TCM) and the theory of conceptual integration (TCI). The main types of conceptual metaphor and the cognitive mechanisms are explained. On the basis of a comparative analysis, difference and relationships between TCM and TCI are investigated.

Key words: cognitive science, cognitive linguistics, cognitive model, conceptual integration, metaphor, theory of conceptual metaphor and theory of conceptual integration, the target domain and the source domain.

Language, as an instrument of linguistic science, has always been a bond between thinking and the surrounding world. Scientists have been interested in the questions of human thinking in its relationship with language for not only in recent decades, associated with the development of cognitive sciences, but for centuries. Every period in linguistics offers different answers, depending on the prevailing scientific paradigm and develops a theoretical framework and methodological tools, combining a number of disciplines, among which an important role belongs to cognitive linguistics.

Cognitive linguistics studies ways of obtaining, processing, storing, and using verbalized knowledge. This is knowledge not only about the language itself, but also knowledge about the world gained through the language. Thus, in this case, we are not dealing with a reflection of reality, but with its interpretation. Interpretation is a cognitive operation that is based on stable "cognitive models". A

cognitive model should be understood as a database structure with cognitive operations applied to it. Such database is based on idealized cognitive models, which, according to J. S. Lakoff, are the structures of human knowledge [Lakoff, Johnson, 1980]. This means that the ability to interpret the world is an innate characteristic of a person, and cognitive operations (receiving and transmitting information) are regulated by relatively constant cognitive models. And this theoretical foundation arises the theory of conceptual metaphor and as its continuation and expansion - the theory of conceptual integration or blending. Metaphor is as a cognitive mechanism which explains the phenomena of language and speech.

In the twentieth century, metaphor became a phenomenon that unites research in various fields of knowledge and forms a new vector of scientific research. Works in the field of conceptual metaphor gave motivation to the study of cognitive processes of consciousness. Metaphorical thinking is manifested in the metaphorical nature of language, where metaphor acts as an important mental operation that forms a way of knowing, categorizing, conceptualizing, evaluating and explaining the world. [Grady, et al, 1999]. With the help of metaphor, a person thinks and learns about the world in which he lives.

Theory of conceptual metaphor (TCM) and theory of conceptual integration (TCI) are closely connected with each other. It should be noted that TCI was developed by J. Fauconnier and M. Turner on the basis of the theory of mental spaces [Fauconnier, 1997] in order to improve the theory of conceptual metaphor by J. S. Miller. Lakoff and M. Johnson [Lakoff, Johnson 1999]. This new search was prompted by TCM's inability to explain individual metaphors based on conventional relationships between the two conceptospheres. Thus, the first fundamental difference between these two theories is the number and quality of the basic sources of entry into the conceptual metaphor, which in TCM are called domains, and in TCI mental spaces.

In TCM, metaphors are analyzed as "a stable and systematic relationship between two conceptual domains" – the target domain (the conceptual sphere of the

target) and the source domain (the conceptual sphere of the source). The target domain, which is interpreted through a conceptual metaphor, is a conceptual referent, and the source domain being compared is a conceptual correlate. The referent and the correlate must belong to different conceptual spaces, that is, be "divorced in thought" [Grady et al, 1999]. Thus, in TCM we are dealing with a form of conceptualization that relates not to individual objects, but to areas of social experience, which in turn are correlated through metaphor with simpler spaces that can be observed through the transfer of the nature of the conceptualization of space.

In TCI, unlike TCM, the main element of cognitive organization is not the domain, but the mental space. Mental spaces are compact formats of knowledge interconnected within the discourse, which can be modified as it unfolds. Mental spaces are not equal to a domain, but rather depend on it: they represent certain scenarios that are structured by domains. This means that mental spaces are generated online in the process of communication and are unique to a particular situation, while domains represent more general structures of knowledge that are associated with permanent areas of the thinking space.

A significant difference between the two theories is also their structural organization. TCM analysis operates by mapping between two conceptual structures, while TCI provides for connections between several (at least four) mental spaces.

After analyzing TCM and TCI, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Both theories are based on metaphor as a cognitive mechanism, which provides the processes of perception, processing and transmission of information about the surrounding world;
2. In TCM, metaphors are analyzed as permanent relationships between two conceptual spheres, while in TCI metaphors are refracted through mental spaces, which are short-term formations that are modified as discourse unfolds;
3. TCM is based on conventional conceptual metaphors, and TCI explains new metaphorical conceptualizations that reflect the author's idiosyncrasies;

4. Both theories reveal the cognitive processes of both logical and imaginative thinking, making them a powerful tool for interpretation.

The cognitive approach to the analysis of metaphor occupies a leading place in modern science, and the application of the theory of conceptual metaphor and the theory of conceptual integration are inextricably connected. In our opinion, the application of TCM and TCI in our practical research should provide an impetus to the study of metaphor as a mechanism of cognition.

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